

A reproductively active population of *Talisman scrobilator* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Caenogastropoda, Tonnoidea) in the southeast coast of the Iberian Peninsula, with a report on reproduction and feeding habits

Una población reproductivamente activa de *Talisman scrobilator* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Caenogastropoda, Tonnoidea) en el sudeste de la Península Ibérica, con registro de los hábitos de reproducción y alimentación

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ABSTRACT

An apparently stable and reproductively active population of *Talisman scrobilator* (Gastropoda, Bursidae) is reported in the Hornillo Bay, Murcia, on the southeast coast of the Iberian Peninsula. Five specimens were collected and maintained in aquarium, which permitted the observation of a mating event. Approximately 40 days after copulation, the female started oviposition, which took 8-9 days to be completed, also forming an incubation structure on the shell to protect the egg-mass. The egg-mass structure is studied, as well as the embryonic development of the larvae until hatching and the maternal care of the female during this period. The complete process in aquarium conditions, from the copulation to the hatching of the veliger larvae, lasted a total of 104 days. The sampled capsules shortly before hatching contained ca. 1500 veligers in the larger capsules placed in the middle of the egg-mass and ca. 400 in the smaller ones from the periphery. With ca. 200 capsules in the egg-mass, the number of veligers that reach this phase is estimated in a range of 80,000-300,000 (a mean of $\approx 190,000$), of which only $\approx 43,000$ survived after 8 days that lasted the hatching.

Several species of annelids, molluscs and echinoderms were offered as potential prey to the aquarium specimens, of which only *Marthasterias glacialis* was preyed on, without the attack being lethal to the starfish. It has also been observed that the same attack mechanism used for predation is used as a self-defence method.

RESUMEN

Se reseña la existencia de una población, aparentemente estable y reproductivamente activa de *Talisman scrobilator* (Gastropoda, Bursidae), en la Bahía del Hornillo, Murcia, en el sudeste de la Península Ibérica. Cinco ejemplares fueron recolectados y mantenidos en acuario, lo cual permitió observar un evento de apareamiento. Aproximadamente unos

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40 días después de la cópula, la hembra comenzó el proceso de oviposición, la cual duró entre 8 y 9 días, formando también una estructura de incubación en la concha para proteger la masa de huevos. Se ha estudiado la estructura y características de la masa ovígera así como el desarrollo embrionario de las larvas hasta su eclosión y el comportamiento maternal de la hembra en ese periodo. El proceso completo en condiciones de acuario, desde la cópula hasta la eclosión de las larvas veliger, duró un total de 104 días. Las cápsulas muestreadas poco antes de la eclosión contenían unas 1500 velígeras en las cápsulas más grandes situadas en la parte central de la masa de huevos y unas 400 en las más pequeñas de la periferia. Se han contado unas 200 cápsulas en la puesta, y el número de velígeras que alcanzan este estado se estima en un rango de 80.000-300.000 (una media de ≈ 190.000), de las cuales sólo ≈ 43.000 sobrevivieron a los 8 días que duró la eclosión.

Varias especies de anélidos, moluscos y equinodermos fueron ofrecidas individualmente como presas potenciales a los ejemplares del acuario, pero solo *Marthasterias glacialis* fue depredada, sin que el ataque fuera letal para dicho equinodermo. Se ha observado también que el mismo mecanismo de ataque para alimentarse es usado como método de defensa.

KEY WORDS: *Bursidae*, Mediterranean, Mollusca, population, reproduction, feeding.

PALABRAS CLAVE: *Bursidae*, Mediterráneo, Mollusca, población, reproducción, alimentación.

INTRODUCTION

The family *Bursidae* Thiele, 1925 comprises a moderately diversified group of carnivorous gastropods with approximately 60 recent species (MOLLUSCABASE, 2020). The emblematic species known as *Bursa scrobilator* (Linnaeus, 1758) received the new combination *Talisman scrobilator* (Linnaeus, 1758) following a recent phylogenetic reconstruction of the family by SANDERS ET AL. (2021), using molecular characters.

The current distribution of *Bursidae* is limited to the tropical and subtropical waters, and to a lesser extent the temperate waters, of the globe (COSSIGNANI, 1994). The species included in the genus *Bursa* before the phylogenetic reconstruction of SANDERS ET AL. (2021), and recorded in the Macaronesian region are: *Alanbeuella corrugata* (Perry, 1811), *Lampasopsis thomae* (d'Orbigny, 1847), *Tritonoranella ranelloides* (Reeve, 1844) and *Talisman scrobilator*, the latter being the only species of the group recorded from the Mediterranean Sea. There are isolated records of this species in the Garraf coast (LÓPEZ SORIANO & TARRUELLA RUESTES, 2002; TARRUELLA

RUESTES & LOPEZ SORIANO, 2004.), Nice (France), Savona (Italy) (LANDAU, BEU & MARQUET, 2004), southern Italy, Sicily and Malta (SMRIGLIO ET AL., 2019), these being the northernmost locations for any member of the family *Bursidae*.

In a recent review, SMRIGLIO ET AL. (2019) considered that *T. scrobilator* belongs to a species complex derived from an Atlantic species which originated in the Paratethys, descendant of *Bursa nodosa* (Borson, 1825), now extinct (SANDERS, MERLE & PUILANDRE, 2019). The connection between the Atlantic Ocean and Mediterranean Sea was closed during the late Messinian "salinity crisis" 5.9-5.3 M.a. (JOLIVET ET AL., 2006), and *T. scrobilator* disappeared from the Mediterranean waters (SANDERS ET AL., 2019), being reintroduced back when the Atlantic waters penetrated again in the western basin (in the Zanclean stage). For a long period of time, *T. scrobilator* and *A. corrugata* coexisted in the warm waters of the proto-Mediterranean (JUÁREZ-RUIZ, 2018). During the late Pleistocene *A. corrugata* disappeared from the Mediter-

ranean (LANDAU, HARZHAUSER & BEU, 2009), coinciding with its maximum diffusion in Pacific waters, and the populations of *T. scrobilator* decreased.

Before the Messinian event, *T. scrobilator* was established in the warm waters on both Atlantic shores (fossil records in Costa Rica; Beu, 2010) and Mediterranean (CUERDA, 1957), expanding along the Atlantic coast of the Iberian Peninsula as far north as Galicia, and along the African coast as far south as Senegal. Another recent study (CROCETTA *ET AL.* 2019) based on molecular features confirmed that the recent specimens from the Macaronesian region and Mediterranean belong to a single clade, being this clade sister of the samples from Senegal. *Talisman scrobilator* colonized practically the entire western and central Mediterranean basin. However, the climatic oscillations of cold glacial and warm interglacial periods during the Quaternary led to the successive regression and expansion of the species. Apart from specific points in the central Mediterranean and Alborán sea, the records of the species in the western basin have been extremely scarce recently.

Despite not being mentioned in the *Catálogo Español de Especies Amenazadas* (2011), probably due to lack of data, the species is included in the *Libro Rojo de los Invertebrados de Andalucía* (BAREA-AZCÓN, BALLESTEROS-DUPERÓN & MORENO, 2008), barely providing data about its occurrence and giving general recommendations for its protection. In addition, *T. scrobilator* has been mentioned as “species in regression” in the western Mediterranean (VERDEJO, 2001). In contrast, the scattered reports of the species from the central Mediterranean (northern Sicily, Calabria, Gulf of Naples) of living specimens (TRILLÓ, 2001, SMRIGLIO *ET AL.*, 2019) support the subsistence of populations in these waters. In fact, SMRIGLIO *ET AL.* (2019), based on molecular data, suggest that the demography of this species has remained stable in recent times, and that the warming of the Mediterranean waters could encourage its expansion.

On the other hand, the Canary Islands are considered as an important reservoir of the species, with the presence of stable populations (VEGA LUZ, 1996), especially around the island of Tenerife. VERDEJO (2001) pointed out that the dispersion of larvae from this area and their transport by currents in the Atlantic water masses that penetrate through the Gibraltar Strait could lead to the sporadic presence of the species in certain locations of the western Mediterranean. In addition, taking into account the presumed long permanence of veliger larvae in the plankton (CROCETTA *ET AL.*, 2019), the possibility that some of these larvae are transported to and develop in areas of the central basin should be considered.

The present work documents the presence of a population of *Talisman scrobilator* on the coast of Murcia, in an area where it had never been reported before, and expands the knowledge of this species in the western Mediterranean, thanks to the discovery of several specimens and reproductive pairs in their natural habitat. Also, the reproduction, feeding and behavioural habits in captivity are described herein, aiming to substantially increase knowledge about this species.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out in Hornillo Bay, Murcia, in the southeastern Iberian Peninsula, between the end of September and November 2019, in an area of approximately 2 km² between 6 and 10 metres deep in rocky enclaves. The shore in this area is abrupt and the bottoms are mainly hard, composed of piled rocks with abundant cavities and comprising a complex littoral habitat with moderate wave action. The sessile biota on this bottom is abundant and leads to a sciaphilic/precocalligenous community, favoured by a weak light incidence. This rocky environment was limited by soft sandy/bioclastic bottoms mostly occupied by patches of *Posidonia oceanica*. The average temperature of the water at those depths during the study was around 18°C.

Of the specimens studied, it was possible to follow the evolution of one (Fig. 1K) of the two individuals with spawn *in-situ* for some weeks –with interruptions due to bad weather. Concurrently, five specimens (two pairs and a solitary specimen) were maintained in a 45 l aquarium with a filtration and aeration system. This was placed in a shaded spot with no direct light incidence in order to simulate as much as possible their natural environment, with hard substrate and some associated fauna. No temperature control device was used, but water temperature remained between 17°C and 20°C throughout the study. The water was completely renewed approximately every two weeks.

Shortly before the hatching of larvae in the aquarium, two egg capsules were sampled, a larger one from the central part of the egg-mass and a smaller one from the peripheral zone, in order to count the number of veligers per capsule. Another two freshly laid capsules (Fig. 2D) and another capsule 21 days after being deposited (Fig. 2E) were also sampled from the specimen studied *in-situ*.

To estimate the survival rate in aquarium conditions after the hatching period, once all the veligers hatched, the water of the aquarium was drained out with a tube. The living veligers were dispersed homogeneously (dead larvae sedimented to the bottom due to lack of mobility) in a known volume of water, and 100 samples of 10 ml each were randomly taken. The larvae from each sample were counted to obtain the average number of surviving veligers after hatching was completed.

In captivity, feeding was a problem initially. It was attempted with the polychaetes *Serpula vermicularis* Linnaeus, 1767 and with species of the genera *Nereis* and *Leodice*, with the bivalves *Arca noae* Linnaeus, 1758, *Neopycnodonte cochlear* (Poli, 1795) and *Venus verrucosa* Linnaeus, 1758, as well as with the echinoderms *Paracentrotus lividus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Phyllophorus urna* Grube, 1840, *Ophidiaster ophidianus* (Lamarck,

1816) and *Echinaster sepositus* (Retzius, 1758), considered as potential prey for being present in the habitat where the specimens of *T. scrobilator* were found. They have also shared the aquarium with some specimens of *Monoplex parthenopeus* (Salis Marschlins, 1793). Finally, the asteroid *Marthasterias glacialis* (Linnaeus, 1758) was tested, being scarce but present in the study area.

The studied specimens were the following (max. length x max. width):

(E1) Pair 1 (male) 67.7 x 37.0 mm (Figs. 1A-B)

(E2) Pair 1 (female) 65.9 x 35.0 mm (Figs. 1C-D)

(E3) Pair 2 (reproductive male) 51.0 x 27.3 mm (Figs. 1E-F)

(E4) Pair 2 (reproductive female) 73.9 x 44.2 (Figs. 1G-H, 2C, 3A-F)

(E5) Solitary (male) 44.8 x 25.3 mm (Figs. 1I-J)

(E6) Specimen *in-situ* (female) 74.0 x 39.6 mm (Fig. 1K)

Five of the specimens (one pair (Pair 2, figs. 1E-H), two female specimens, each one with their corresponding egg-masses (Fig. 1K) and one solitary specimen (Figs. 1I-J)) were found in an area of approximately 100 m². Another pair (Pair 1, Figs. 1A-D) was found in another similar rocky enclave located nearby at a distance of 1.2 km.

The photos were taken with a digital camera and processed with a photo edition program (Adobe Photoshop). Larvae counting and detail photos were made under stereo microscope. The applied systematic is based on the recent phylogenetic reconstruction of SANDERS *ET AL.* (2021).

RESULTS

Observations *in-situ*

It was possible to follow one specimen and its egg-mass (Fig. 1K) *in-situ* weekly for a few weeks during October and November 2019. This specimen (E6) was found during mid-October, in the final stages of the egg-laying process, placing the last capsules of the spawn

Figure 1. Studied specimens of *Talisman scrobilator*, Hornillo Bay, Águilas, Murcia. A-J. Specimens studied in aquarium. A, B: male specimen from the first pair (E1) (67.7 x 37.0 mm); C, D: female specimen from the first pair (E2) (65.9 x 35.0 mm); E, F: specimen from the second pair, reproductive male (E3) (51.0 x 27.3 mm); G, H: specimen from the second pair, reproductive female (E4) (73.9 X 44.2 mm); I, J: single specimen, male (E5) (44.8 x 25.3 mm). K. Female specimen with eggs tracked *in-situ* (second week) (74.0 x 39.6 mm).

*Figura 1. Ejemplares de Talisman scrobilator estudiados, Bahía del Hornillo, Águilas, Murcia. A-J. Ejemplares estudiados en acuario. A, B: ejemplar macho de la primera pareja (E1) (67,7 x 37,0 mm); C, D: ejemplar hembra de la primera pareja (E2) (65,9 x 35,0 mm); E, F: ejemplar de la segunda pareja, macho reproductor (E3) (51,0 x 27,3 mm); G, H: ejemplar de la segunda pareja, hembra reproductora (E4) (73,9 X 44,2 mm); I, J: ejemplar macho aislado (E5) (44,8 x 25,3 mm). K. Ejemplar (hembra) con puesta observado *in-situ* (segunda semana) (74,0 x 39,6 mm).*

–two capsules were sampled at that moment (Fig. 2D) - in a narrow cavity carved inside a wide crevice at 9 metres depth. The bottom there is composed of large, piled rocks affected by the biological activity of the dominant sciaphilic/precocalligenous community. The most abundant organisms in this community were represented by sciaphilic algae, solitary and colonial stony corals, bryozoans, ascidians, sponges and polychaetes. There are also echinoderms such as *Marthasterias glacialis*, *Ophidiaster ophidianus*, *Echinaster sepositus*, *Ophioderma longicauda* (Bruzellius, 1805) and *Arbacia lixula* (Linnaeus, 1758), some of them considered as potential prey, as well as bivalves like *Barbatia barbata* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Arca noae* Linnaeus, 1758, *Lima lima* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Mimachlamys varia* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *Lithophaga lithophaga* (Linnaeus, 1758).

One week later the specimen was found to be in the same position, and no evident changes were observed in the egg-mass. The following week it was not possible to sample due to adverse weather conditions. The next week, in early November, the specimen was still in the same position, but the egg-mass had acquired a dark bluish/brown colouring, a sign that the larvae had entered the intracapsular veliger stage with a small larval shell. One capsule was sampled at that time (Fig. 2F). No further observations *in-situ* could take place due to adverse weather conditions. During some of these dives, other empty egg-capsule masses were found nearby, that appeared to have been abandoned for some time, and resembled very much the one laid by *Talisman*

scrobilator. It is not possible to confirm that they belong to this species, since the egg-masses of certain ranellids like *Monoplex parthenopeus*, also present in the study area, are very similar.

Observations in aquarium

Of the five specimens that were maintained and studied in aquarium, the copulation between the specimens of one of the pairs was observed (Figs. 1E-H, 3A) and the monitoring of the complete process of spawning, larval development and hatching (Figs. 3E-F) was possible.

Reproductive behaviour and spawning:

Two weeks after the introduction of the specimens in the aquarium, in October 11, 2019, mating between one of the pairs (E3 & E4) was observed (Fig. 3A), that lasted several hours. As it usually occurs in Caenogastropoda, fertilization is internal and crossed. Approximately 40 days after copulation, the female (E4) started egg-laying in a corner of the aquarium. The egg-mass starts being deposited from its central part and towards the outside, in a more or less concentric pattern. It begins with the secretion of a gelatinous mucous base attached to the substrate, which hardens and will end up forming a translucent whitish/yellowish, concave and almost cylindrical case, in whose interior the egg-capsules will be deposited (Fig. 3B). These capsules are cylindrical and laterally flattened (although they end up having a vertically rectangular or triangular shape when they are packed), broader at the base and narrower apically. The capsules are 8.5 to 12.3 mm in height, 4-4.8 mm wide at the base, 2.4-2.6 mm wide at the apical part and 2.0-

(Right page) Figure 2. A, B: *Talisman scrobilator* feeding in aquarium (A: *T. scrobilator* reaching *Marthasterias glacialis* with its proboscis to feed on its soft tissues while it flees; B: *T. scrobilator* feeding on a detached harm of *M. glacialis* after attack); C: *T. scrobilator* on the egg-mass in aquarium; D: *T. scrobilator* egg-capsules just laid by the specimen tracked *in-situ* with embryos in egg phase; E: detail of a peripheral capsule laid in aquarium with veligers right before hatching (V) and undeveloped eggs (Ue); F: egg capsule obtained 21 days after the egg laying of the specimen *in-situ* with larvae in veliger phase. Abbreviations, Li: incubation lip; Pr: proboscis; Aw: post-attack wound; Ue: undeveloped eggs; V: veligers.

Figura 2. A, B: *Talisman scrobilator* alimentándose en acuario (A: *T. scrobilator* alcanzando con la proboscide a *Marthasterias glacialis* para alimentarse de sus tejidos blandos mientras huye; B: *T. scrobilator* alimentándose de un brazo desprendido de *M. glacialis* tras atacarla); C: *T. scrobilator* con puesta en el acuario; D: cápsulas ovigeras de *T. scrobilator* recién depositadas por el ejemplar observado in-situ con embriones en fase de huevo; E: detalle de una cápsula periférica depositada en acuario con larvas velíferas (V) poco antes de la eclosión y huevos no desarrollados (Ue); F: cápsula obtenida 21 días después de la puesta del ejemplar in-situ con larvas en fase de velíger. Abreviaturas, Li: labio incubador; Pr: proboscide; Aw: herida post-ataque; Ue: huevos no desarrollados; V: velíferas.

2.3 mm thick. They are transparent and the interior can be clearly observed. The capsules located on the periphery of the egg-mass are smaller than those located centrally. The freshly laid eggs are distributed over the inner surface of the capsule and also form a small column rising from the base of the capsule. When the larvae acquire mobility this distribution is disordered. The embryos are immersed in a transparent liquid matrix. The female (E4) took 8-9 days to complete the egg-laying and remained immobile over the egg-mass during the period of incubation until hatching. The whole egg-mass is about 46 mm in diameter.

During oviposition, the mantle of the female remained extended over the egg-mass. The result is the creation of a thin extension or overgrowth of ostracum on the lip (Figs. 1G-H, 2C and 3F), resembling a ledge that covers the entire opening of the egg-mass. This extension was formed during the 8-9 days that the spawning lasted, and helped to keep the egg-mass protected during incubation. There are no previous records of this structure in the literature, which from now on will be referred to as an "incubation lip". This thin and fragile structure will easily deteriorate as soon as the female abandons the egg-mass after hatching, due to abrasion with hard surfaces. The specimen E6 also developed this incubation lip.

Larval development: The non-segmented embryos are spherical, have a pale yellow colouration conferred by the vitellus (Fig. 2D) and are $140 \pm 20 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter. As the embryos progressed through maturation stages, the coloration of the egg-mass varied (Figs. 3B-E).

Some of the early segmentation stages were observed, but could not be clearly differentiated. At 7 days after the end of spawning, motile ciliated trochophore larvae were observed in the last deposited capsules, which gave the egg-mass a darker yellow colour. At 20 days after the end of the spawning, the capsules begin to take on a dark bluish brown colour (Fig. 3D), as the yolk is absorbed. The larvae begin to enter the

early veliger stage, showing a small embryonic shell (protoconch I), matching those observed in the capsules sampled *in-situ* (Fig. 1K). There was a high activity of the ciliated velum. As there is a lapse period of around 8 days between the beginning and the end of the egg-laying, the maturation of the larvae is not homogeneous in time. Those in the periphery mature later and therefore acquire this colour after, as the larvae of the capsules deposited in the center of the egg-mass mature concentrically in order of deposition.

After 53-55 days from the beginning of the egg-laying, the first veligers started to hatch, also from those capsules located in the center of the egg-mass. These free veligers had a dextral larval shell (protoconch I) of $250\text{-}270 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter with 0.5 whorls, brown colour, with a fine and densely granulated sculpture. The soft parts comprise a foot with a small operculum, a velum with two rounded and ciliated lobes, and two black eyes which contrast with the rest of the body, unpigmented. The female remained over the egg-mass covering it with the incubation lip throughout the whole process, without leaving that position until the end of the hatching (Fig. 3F).

The hatching takes place through an apical hole in the capsule of $1.7 \times 0.7 \text{ mm}$. The factor that triggers the appearance of this hole is unknown, presumably an enzymatic action. The hatching of the larvae from all the capsules lasted 8 days and ended January 23, 2020. The veligers had a size of $300 \pm 20 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter.

The complete process of breeding in aquarium conditions, from copulation to the hatching of all the veliger larvae, lasted a total of 104 days.

The count of the sampled capsules shortly before hatching resulted in 1490 (≈ 1500) veligers in the larger capsule from the central part of the egg-mass and ≈ 400 in the smaller capsule from the peripheral part. This shows a great variability in the number of larvae per capsule. It must be taken into account that not all the eggs reach this phase,

Figure 3. Phases of the reproductive process of *Talisman scrobilator* in aquarium. A: copulation between E3 and E4; B: E4 and the egg-mass one day after the laying started; C: E4 just finished spawning; D: E4 and egg-mass 26 days after spawning; E: E4 and egg-mass 35 days after spawning; F: complete exit of veligers 46 days after being laid. Abbreviations, Li: incubation lip; Pn: penis.

Figura 3. Fases del proceso de reproducción de Talisman scrobilator en acuario. A: cópula entre E3 y E4; B: E4 y puesta un día después del comienzo; C: E4 y puesta recién terminada; D: E4 y puesta a los 26 días de ser depositada; E: E4 y puesta a los 35 días de ser depositada; F: salida completa de velígeras a los 46 días después de ser depositadas. Abreviaciones, Li: labio de incubación; Pn: pene.

with some remaining undeveloped –nurse eggs? The proportion of these undeveloped eggs in the different capsules was uneven, the majority remaining in the peripheral capsules. In the peripheral capsule sampled for veligers counting (Fig. 2E), the undeveloped eggs comprised about half of the capsules content, while the more centric capsules barely had any undeveloped eggs remaining.

The study of the empty egg-mass provided a count total of 204 capsules (≈ 200). Considering the number of capsules and veliger larvae (alive or not, based on the larval shells) per capsule, the total number of larvae reaching this phase is between $\approx 80,000$ (based on smaller capsules) and $\approx 300,000$ (based on the larger capsules), with an average of $\approx 190,000$.

A high mortality rate of the veligers was observed during the hatching period, especially during the first hours after leaving the capsules, and some died even before hatching. An average of 9.56 larvae per 10 ml (0.956 veligers/ml) were counted after the hatching of the whole egg-mass. The volume of water was 45 litres, so the number of viable larvae is estimated to only $\approx 43,000$. This indicates that the survival rate during the first week in aquarium conditions was $\approx 22.63\%$. However, it is unsure whether these survival rates are similar to those occurring in the wild or if were due to artificial conditions, where trophic requirements have a critical role.

After being counted, these viable veligers were released to the wild at the same location where the reproductive specimens were found, as there were no adequate resources available for their continued maintenance.

Feeding habits and behaviour: No interest was observed in the presence of any of the species proposed as potential prey. However, when introducing *Marthasterias glacialis* into the aquarium, the specimens of *T. scrobilator* showed an immediate reaction of interest, which allowed to observe the feeding process. The first step consisted in locating and

chasing the asteroid, apparently by chemotaxis, as the inhalant siphon points in its direction. Once near the asteroid, the huge intense-black proboscis, which can stretch to be as long as the shell length, is evaginated, and explores the surface of the echinoderm, which sets out in escape. From that moment two scenarios may occur; in one of them, since *Marthasterias glacialis* is a strong and active echinoderm, what *T. scrobilator* does on certain occasions is to insert the proboscis into the oral side of one arm through the ambulacral groove or cause a wound to an arm and quickly scrape as much as possible of the soft parts from the asteroid before it escapes (Fig. 2A). The other possible scenario takes place when *T. scrobilator* strongly grasps a spine of the echinoderm using the proboscis, causing it enough stress for it to detach the attacked arm, permitting the asteroid to escape. This second situation allows *T. scrobilator* to easily feed from the autotomized arm (Fig. 2B). In both cases, the prey on which they were feeding survived.

A defensive behaviour under threat or irritation was also observed, reacting to it by the evagination of the proboscis in search of the soft parts of the aggressor or disturber. One of the reported situations took place between two specimens of the same sex, were one of them crawled on top of the other. The disturbing specimen retracted violently after receiving the defensive attack. One of the specimens also tried to defend itself when sampled for the study.

Generally there was little activity observed among the specimens, suggesting eminently sedentary habits with peaks of nocturnal activity.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In the present work the presence of a reproductively active population of *Talisman scrobilator* is reported from the coast of Murcia, on the southeast Iberian Peninsula.

It is assumed that Tonnoidea larvae generally have a long pelagic phase.

SHELTEMA (1971) reports the presence of *Bursidae* larvae in plankton samples obtained from different stations in the Atlantic Ocean. This data, considering the relation between the speed of the currents and the estimated minimum duration of the planktonic phase of larvae reinforces the idea of a trans-oceanic dispersion as justification for the wide-ranging distribution of the group.

It is difficult to estimate how long ago this population settled in the area, as well as the extension and if there are other similar populations along the Levantine coast. However, the size of some specimens and the finding of a fresh and mature shell around a decade ago in the same study area indicate that the population must have been established at least several years ago.

Among the hypotheses on the origin of the specimens that colonized this area, the most plausible are that they may have come from undiscovered nearby populations located more to the east of the study area, or from the central Mediterranean. It is considered likely that the Almería-Orán front (AO) would restrict the arrival of larvae from the southwest of the peninsula (Atlantic and Alborán) to this specific area, which leaves as less probable, although not impossible, the Atlantic origin of the colonizing larvae. The duration of the pelagic phase, the density of larvae in the meroplankton and their survival rates are essential parameters for the species to extend into areas appropriate for development and survival as adults, with an adequate number of individuals that permits the successful development of a reproductively active population, rather than a few isolated individuals.

The presence of the species in the area appears to be related to the increasing temperature of the Mediterranean in recent years (0.3°C per decade) (MARBÁ ET AL., 2015), among other factors, such as the suitability of the environment and its reproductive dynamics.

Several works deal with the reproduction and development processes of various tonnoidean species: RIEDEL (1995) gathered data on this aspect from

species like *Dulcerana granularis* (Röding, 1798), *Alanbeuella corrugata*, *Lampasopsis rhodostoma* (G. B. Sowerby II, 1835), *Bufo naria echinata* (Link, 1807) and *Tutufa bufo* (Röding, 1798). This author pointed out that the egg-masses are incubated by most of these species and noted the number of capsules between 100 and 150 per spawn. The egg-mass in *A. corrugata* contained more than 100,000 embryos (D'Asaro, 1969, cited in RIEDEL, 1995). It is also noted that the diameters of the embryonic shells of these species (formerly included in the genus *Bursa*) are between 150-320 µm (RIEDEL, 1995 and references therein). These data are similar and agree with those obtained from *Talisman scrobilator* in the present study, with about 200 capsules in the spawn and 190,000 larvae whose shells measure 250-270 µm in diameter.

Other larger Tonnoidea present in the Mediterranean lay larger egg-masses; *Charonia lampas* (Linnaeus, 1758) deposits between 200 and 400 capsules in spawns that last about 20 days, where around 200,000-800,000 veligers hatch with shell diameters of 280 ± 20 µm after 3 to 5 months of incubation (CAVALLARO ET AL., 2016). In *Charonia sequezuae* (Aradas & Benoit, 1872) spawning can take place between 3 and 95 days after copulation (sperm storage) (DOXA, KENTOURI & DIVANACH, 2019). In both previous species, maternal care behavior is reported. *Tonna galea* (Linnaeus, 1758) lays about 3,000-3,200 capsules in a gelatinous-matrix rosette with about 320,000 embryos. Mobile trochophore larvae are observed at day 11 and veligers hatch at day 34 with larval shells of 489 ± 10,7 µm in diameter (DOXA ET AL., 2011). SHELTEMA (1971) estimated the duration of the pelagic stage of *T. galea* in 242 days. It is assumed that the timing of these processes vary according to environmental and individual conditions.

However, no data have been found in the literature on the duration from copulation to egg-laying, nor from incubation to hatching in *Bursidae*. In the present study it was observed that the

oviposition of *T. scrobilator* took place 40 days after mating, in mid-November, and needed 8-9 days to be completed. Seven days after being deposited, motile ciliated trocophore larvae were observed in the capsules, and 20 days after being laid, larvae began to develop larval shells, entering the early veliger phase. After 46 days of intracapsular development the veligers hatch, needing about 8-9 days for all to hatch. The duration of the pelagic phase remains unknown.

During the whole process, both E6 (during the period in which it could be studied *in-situ*), and E4 (until the complete hatching of the larvae), remained over their respective egg-masses covering them, evidencing protective behaviour and maternal care. Both specimens produced a thin overgrowth structure of ostracum on the lip, mainly in the region of the outer lip, but also in the parietal lip, during the spawning period. This structure is not mentioned before in the literature and it has been herein named "incubation lip". The incubation lip served as a cover to protect the egg-mass during the entire incubation period. After hatching, the fragile incubation lip rapidly deteriorates due to abrasion with surfaces. Even after its deterioration, the formation of the incubation lip is still evident by forming layers that thicken the lip. The count of this accumulation of layers can be used to deduce the number of spawns that a specimen has made, and therefore the reproductive capacity, as well as the point when sexual maturity is reached. This can surely be extrapolated to other species of *Bursidae* and probably even in other groups, which would suppose a great advance in the knowledge of these molluscs. This topic will be addressed in more detail in subsequent works.

Several studies mention the feeding of different species of Tonnoidea. For example, BANDEL (1984) notes that species previously included in the genus *Bursa* as well as *Cymatium* from the Caribbean Sea feed on other molluscs, annelids and barnacles. BARKALOVA, FEDOSOV & KANTOR (2016) also affirms

that ranellids and bursids are known to have a wide range of potential prey, including molluscs, polychaetes, barnacles and even ascidians, among others. In contrast, there was a complete lack of interest by *T. scrobilator* for any other species that were tested apart from *Marthasterias glacialis*, despite having been without feeding for several weeks and having given them facilities (e.g. breaking the shell of bivalves). In RIEDEL (1995, and references therein) it is indicated that several species of *Bursa* have been observed feeding on asteroids, brittle stars (Ophiuroidea) and echinoids. TAYLOR, MORRIS & TAYLOR (1980) mentions that bursids feed on brittle stars, echinoids, and even crinoids.

MORTON (2012) described the predation of *Charonia lampas* on *Ophidiaster ophidianus*, where a similar process takes place to that observed in *T. scrobilator*, holding the arm of the asteroid causing its autotomization. The consumption of *M. glacialis* is also reported in *Charonia lampas* by MORTON & PIRES (2013) and in *Charonia sequezenae* by DOXA ET AL. (2012).

Other tonnoideans also have a seemingly strict and well-documented diet in both literature and divers pictures and records. This is the case of *Tonna galea*, whose diet consists of holothurians that inhabit the same soft bottoms, being able to gulp them whole with the enormous proboscis (DOXA ET AL., 2011).

The reported behaviour appears to be the usual in *T. scrobilator* and can be related to the high specialization for the prey and the possibility of feeding again in the future due to the low abundance of its prey. It is not excluded that this is a preset behaviour and techniques in both *T. scrobilator* and *M. glacialis*.

In the saliva of almost all Tonnoidea (with the exception of *Personidae*) the presence of sulfuric acid has been reported (BARKALOVA ET AL., 2016). It is known that *Bursidae* such as *Lampasopsis cruentata* (G. B. Sowerby II, 1835) and *Dulcerana granularis* inject acid/venomous saliva into their prey to paralyze them (Hughes & Hughes, 1981, cited in RIEDEL, 1995). By the effects observed in the prey after the attacks, where *M.*

glacialis was clearly affected and slowed down in the cases without autotomization, as well as the immobilized arm in the case with autotomization, it appears that in the diet of *T. scrobilator* this acid/venomous saliva facilitates ingestion, although it has not been chemically confirmed. It also seems that this acid saliva is used as a defence method, as a specimen of *T. scrobilator* was observed evaginating the proboscis searching for the soft parts of another specimen that seemed to be disturbing and invading its space. Once reached, the disturbed specimen quickly retracted the proboscis, and the disturbing specimen, with a short delay of a few seconds, violently retracted completely, and fell off.

Although the results could have been more extensive and accurate if there had been more adequate resources available, especially in the description of early embryogenesis and postlarval

development, this work provides important information on various aspects of the life-cycle of this emblematic species that, until now, were largely unknown. This gives a much broader perspective of their biology and offers facilities when it comes to developing possible appropriate strategies for ecological management (protection-conservation-restoration) in marine ecosystems where this species or similar are involved.

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